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THE MASTERPLANNING TOOLBOX: AN EARLY STAGE DESIGN TOOL FOR THE SYNTHESIS AND EVALUATION OF MULTIMODAL COMPLEXITIES AT A CITY SCALE FOR URBAN DESIGN CONCEPTUALISATION.

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ABSTRACT

Effective city planning requires multimodal analysis at a level which challenges the co-ordination of disciplines and cohesion by the lead designer. The author presents the case for an early design stage tool to complement the growing array of downstream design tools for city design. An early stage tool would improve design conceptualization and provide a live knowledge-base for complex masterplanning issues: the inter-related criteria of a city that create a 'perfect storm' of design requirements - many of which are contradictory and divergent. This paper describes the research and development of the Masterplanning Toolbox, software tool that aims to provide a multi-layered data environment to help synthesize and evaluate urban design proposals at an early stage, developed by the author for the 180 Hectare One North masterplan for Singapore's Jurong Town Corporation, led by Zaha Hadid Architects. The author concludes with reflections on future research.

Keywords: design tools; urban modelling; masterplanning.

INTRODUCTION

The challenge of contemporary urban design is articulated by Walter (Walter, 1988), who argues that we have lost our understanding of the natural and the constructed world, that we exclude human expressiveness, and that we build soulless places. He writes: "For the first time in human history, people are systematically building meaningless places."

The design of cities is complex and historically evolutionary. However, the global rate of urbanization is rising from 13% in 1900 to 50% in 2008, and projected to be 60% by 2030 (UN, 2005). Providing capacity quickly is risky and China for example is accumulating ghost towns that are designed for millions of people. A property bubble drives construction of up to 20 new cities each year, even though there are over 64 million empty homes (Mail, 2010). At the same time, the idea of a high-tech prototype "instant" city is taking shape in the form of Songdo City, South Korea, for completion in 2014 (Gale International, 2010). Gale International, the private developers, hope to sell 20 versions of this city to China, India and Vietnam. But Songdo is unproven and rolling out copies of a prototype globally clearly carries the risks highlighted by Walter.

Historically, the opportunity to design a city entirely from scratch has been rare. Many cities have been around for centuries and were rarely designed as a whole. There are some notable examples of extensive 'renovation' such as that of medieval Paris by Haussmann for Napoleon in the 1850's. Rare examples of tabula rasa design are Modernism's archetypes for city planning and design: Le Corbusier's Chandigarh in India and Oscar Niemeyer's Brasilia with Lúcio Costa. Both of these date from the 1950's and now world heritage sites. In essence, with a few notable examples, cities generally evolve in a responsive, dynamic and evolutionary manner.

Against this background, urban designers require new tools to cope with the need to design precincts,

districts, or even entire cities in a short time frame that is historically unprecedented.

The author's of existing tools indicates that there are six categories. The tools are broadly ranked below in the order in which they have become significant as readily available and useful tools for city designers:

1. Computer-aided design 1960's
2. Management information systems 1970's
3. Visualization 1980's
4. Simulation 1990's
5. Procedural / generative 2000's
6. Time-based evolutionary 2010's

These tools offer spectacular power to the designer of a city in terms of speed of design, detail and scale. However, computational design tools are hard to use in the "upstream" conceptualization of a design at the planning stage. According to Hudson (Hudson, 1979), this stage requires 'foresight in formulating and implementing programs and policies' - a process which he argues is fraught when applying a system of rational planning, and he makes the case for a fluid combination of analytic and subjective approaches. In terms of digital tools that support the conceptual stage, even the computational integration of a design sketch is still a conundrum (Dorta et al, 2008).

Given that computational design tools are generally unsuitable for idea generation (Coyne & Snodgrass, 1993), (Bilda, 2003), research in the field has been directed more towards computer-supported tools (Stappers & Hennessey, 1999). Hence, this research specifically investigates the idea of a tool that leaves the conceptual creative process in the hands of the designer while providing analytical decision making support in the context of "what if" scenarios.

An urban design concept is typically created using plan, section and elevation sketches along with rough 3D massing models. At this early stage, the work is intuitive and reliant on the tacit knowledge of the designer and their technical support team. The author argues that there is a need for tools at this early design stage, to allow rapid "what if"

analysis and feedback to help shape a proposal. Because the subsequent stages of city design tend to be top down, it is imperative that this early stage is as good as it can possibly be. A weak concept will impact negatively on every subsequent design stage. Hence, there is a need for a critical tool that can be used for:

7. Early design conceptualization

This paper describes the Masterplanning Tool developed by the author, which is designed for this early design conceptualization category. This tool aims to improve design conceptualization and provide a live knowledge base to assist in the complexities of developing an effective masterplan for a new city district or a new city.

The inter-related criteria of a city create a 'perfect storm' of design requirements - many of which are contradictory and divergent. Effective city planning requires multimodal analysis at a level that challenges co-ordination of disciplines and cohesion by the lead designer. The aim of the Masterplanning Tool is to provide a software tool that provides a multi-layered data environment to help synthesize and evaluate urban design proposals at an early stage.

The Masterplanning Tool is described, covering the tool's platform, visual object-oriented coding, 2D and 3D data visualization. Innovative algorithm examples are discussed, such as a 'hunter-gatherer' transport node algorithm, and the measurement of the 'vibrancy' of an area in quantitative terms.

The author concludes with a discussion on the tool's usability, ability to meet the original objectives, and reflections on future research.

HYPOTHESIS

The research hypothesis is that a visual/information rich 'what if' tool that allows a design team to play within 'shared design space' (Burry et al, 2005) using multiple planning variables 'on the fly' will enable better concept designs to be created, with reduced risk of abortive work. The likelihood of intractable problems emerging downstream is reduced, allowing

the design team to dedicate more time to refining a design or evaluating more options. Such a software tool would provide a multi-layered data environment to help synthesize and evaluate urban design proposals at an early stage.

RESEARCH APPROACH AND METHOD

An integrated action-based research and user-centred methodology was used to develop the Masterplanning Toolbox, working closely with end users and their clients to establish the scope and specifications, and then to receive feedback from user testing.

The research initiated with ‘dry-run’ studies embedded within practice-based design teams at HTA Architects and Richard Rogers Architects working on significant masterplans. The final Masterplanning Tool software described in the paper was developed by the author as part of the scope of work for the 180 Hectare One North Masterplan for Singapore’s Jurong Town Corporation, led by Zaha Hadid Architects. This plan covers the period 2001-2021.

RESEARCH AND APPLICATIONS IN THE FIELD

Research in the field of urban design tools is benefitting from developments in other areas. The range of applications in which urban modeling methods are important are noted by Vanegas (Vanegas et al, 2010) as:

- Mapping and visualization: re/construction
- Entertainment: games and movies
- Emergency response: training and planning
- Urban planning: predicting outcomes

The development of urban modeling is currently being driven by all of these areas and there is synergy across them.

Research includes Borning’s (Borning et al, 2008) and Ross’s (Ross et al, 2009) work on visually-rich computational tools for planning.

An activity method of design by mapping is also significant. Hillier’s work (Hillier, 1996) on ‘space

syntax’ looks at the movement of people in urban spaces and also creates activity maps of associations. Movement and visibility can then inform the structure of a city.

Vanegas (Vanegas et al, 2010) emphasises the benefit of an integrated approach to visualization and simulation in urban modeling. The most advanced simulations combine procedural modeling techniques with time-based urban simulation to create evolving cities (Weber et al, 2009).

At the highest level of granularity, the activities of simulated people reacting in response to their environment can be modeled. For example, the way in which shoppers are influenced by shop windows as they walk down a street (Chen, 2011).

There is also research that indicates the benefit of allowing a design team to play within ‘shared design space’ when using digital methods (Burry, 2005). There are a number of professional city design software applications, as well as consumer games and serious games. Notable applications are described in this section.

PROFESSIONAL SOFTWARE APPLICATIONS

Numerous GIS are available that combine georeferenced data and digital maps. These include commercial leaders such as Autodesk and Bentley Systems, as well as Open Source GIS applications. GIS provides accurate and visually rich site data for use in combination with other applications.

CityCAD (CityCAD, 2010) is a multidisciplinary tool designed to aid architects, master planners, engineers and users in the early stages of a master plan project. CityCAD was designed to integrate analysis with a design system. It uses a parametric analysis tool that allows city models and schemes to be tested holistically.

The Sustainable Project Appraisal Routine, or SpeAR (Arup, 2011), is a management information system assessment tool by Arup consultants. It is used for balancing the factors that determine whether a project is sustainable or not. SpeAR uses the primary indicators of environmental, natural resources,

societal and economic. The outputs of an analysis are visual graphics in the form of Rose Diagrams.

Archibus (Archibus, 2010) is an information sharing system that allows for the maintenance, management, analysis, data storage and retrieval for an organization's day-to-day operations. Archibus combines real estate, infrastructure and facilities management technologies to work as a web based and central localized tool.

UrbanSim (UrbanSim, 2010) is an innovative Open Source simulation system, which is designed to support urban development through various analytical tools and planning regulations. UrbanSim generates information and simulates the effects and interactions of urban developments by incorporating factors such as land use, transportation, and environmental and economic conditions.

Visual tools are combined with procedural modeling in the CityEngine product offered by Procedural. CityEngine (Procedural, 2011) supports GIS and CAD formats and allows the automated creation of city layouts, buildings and even facades. Procedural modeling of city layouts creates street patterns automatically, although due to the often complex topologies these techniques work best when interactive intervention is also permitted by the user (Lipp et al, 2011). For example, this allows a user to insert square or move a road intersection. These techniques have also come from computer game design research (Kelly G & McCabe, 2007).

No applications were found that emphasized scenario generation in the domain of early stage design.

CONSUMER GAMES

Computer games for the design of cities can provide a sophisticated simulation experience for a user. The best known city simulation game is Sim City, launched in 1989 as a consumer product and updated regularly since. Numerous spin-offs have also been created. Sim City 4, the most recent version that focuses on city creation and management is published by Electronic Arts (Electronic Arts, 2011). Sim City is crude in design terms and imposes a grid-based city plan on users. When new land is

developed, the roads on these grids often fail to align properly. However, the simulator is comprehensive and embraces governance, economics and tax, law, and many socio-cultural factors. This gives the user a holistic insight into the creation and management of cities. Wright, the creator of Sim City comments on the impact of the simulator (Icon Eye, 2004):

“Typically people think of a city or a house or whatever as this static structure, but when you look at it through time, when you fast-forward through decades in a few hours, you start seeing it as this organic, living thing; it has circulation systems, it has cycles that it goes through - some are economic, some are transportation - population demographics, and when you start seeing a city or even a house as a living organism adapting on a long timescale, then it feels more like an organic entity rather than a static entity ... they're part of a greater whole, embedded in another series of designs ... And the layers of design interact with each other on each scales.”

Sim City allows the player to create their own city and respond to various scenarios, including a series of disasters. Scenarios are timed and some are based on real events. The game is now in 3D. In 2008 the source code for the 1990 version of Sim City was released under the free GPL licence as Micropolis - the original name for Sim City.

SERIOUS GAMES

Serious games are games that are used by organizations for training, simulation, team-building and other professional purposes.

IBM's CityOne serious game (CityOne, 2010) runs free online and introduces the concept of managing energy, water, retail and banking sectors across a simulated city. CityOne offers technocratic and commercial control but no design options. The program is simplistic and options are limited. CityOne does usefully raise awareness of the interconnected and complex nature of city management.

Real world, real-time visually accurate simulation requires fast 3D computer graphics. Serious games

typically make use of consumer games technology in this area. There are numerous 3D computer game engines that are available for developers to visualize urban spaces in real-time as “walk throughs”. Many of these engines can be customized and some are freely available. The US-based 3D game pioneers id software (id, 2011) have been releasing their engine code as open source since 1992 under the free GPL licence. The top 3D game engines have been ranked as CryENGINE 3, Gamebryo Lightspeed, and Unreal Engine3 (Develop, 2009). These engines allow the modeling of entire city districts, accurate lighting and rendering of the architecture. They also provide animation and kinetics with artificial intelligence systems for accurately simulating people and vehicles within these environments.

The CryEngine 3 by Germany’s Crytek (Crytek, 2011) is claimed to have the best graphics ever seen (CVG, 2011) - used for a video game called Crysis 2 that was released in March 2011 (Crysis 2, 2011). CryEngine 3 is available as a serious games licence. This includes a “FlowGraph” editor which allows scenarios to be created without the use of source code programming. Licensees include Thales Group, Bechtel and Lockheed Martin.

AIMS OF THE MASTERPLANNING TOOLBOX

Masterplanning a modern city is complex. To be a success, numerous factors must be considered simultaneously. These typically include land use, demographics, transport and infrastructure, environmental impact and economics. Following consultation by the author with architects and urban designers at Richard Rogers Architects, HTA Architects and Zaha Hadid Architects, it was determined that the aims for a software application would be the following:-

- Quick modelling. For testing concept designs
- Rapid feedback. For design factors: transport, infrastructure, energy, etc.
- Dynamic behaviour. Providing dynamic, time-based analysis.
- Information bank. A common store of data for a design team.
- Data linking. Of numerical design information and 2D/3D visualization.

The software application was intended to assist designers, and as such was termed a tool. This contrasts with other designer-free approaches such as procedural or generative systems and other automated/autonomous authoring processes.

The aim of the research was to develop a masterplanning tool with features that could be used at the early stages of a design to consider numerous criteria simultaneously, as well as used downstream during implementation and inevitable modification of a masterplan in the years that follow. These two usage conditions are now described in more detail.

EARLY STAGE DESIGN

The early formation of a masterplan is a stage where typically much use is made of sketches, basic massing study models and the existing experience and expertise of the designers and their technical support team. This can, for example, be a competition stage and is typically time, cost and information limited. One problem with the process is that decisions made early on typically establish the principles of a design in advance of the work being fully tested in terms of relevant design criteria. The consequence is that, while undertaking substantial redesign iterations later on in the design process is usually essential, the time and cost implications limit this activity. Furthermore, clients and teams can be resistant to wholesale redesign of a winning competition proposal. Backtracking is undesirable from a project management viewpoint even if it is essential from a design perspective.

CONTINUING USAGE

A masterplan cannot be fixed in one time - it must allow for unforeseen growth and change over its long maturation cycle. Once a masterplan has been produced and adopted, city authorities may be referring to it for many years as urban fabric is modified or created from scratch. Inevitably, adaptations become necessary over time. These may be initiated by economic or political drivers. Changes may also be caused by the discrepancy between the ideal of the original masterplan and the real of the urban condition. In other instances, errors emerge of a technical nature. However, the

dominant issue is that any long term plan must be predictive and the complexity of a city cannot be projected completely accurately without in-use evaluation. Hence, city managers would benefit from a living masterplan, in a format that allows them to continue to try ‘what if’ scenarios and update the plan over time to reflect reality. This is the second aim of the Masterplanning Toolbox.

EVOLUTIONARY FRAMEWORK

The research method was action-based and took an incremental approach through a user-centred methodology. Features were tried out as mock-ups and then as rapid prototypes for evaluation by users. The scope of the application was initially brainstormed with users from architectural practices. The interlinked factors for the tool were identified during a consultation period that included a technical team. The research initiated with ‘dry-run’ studies embedded within practice-based design teams at HTA Architects and Richard Rogers Architects working on significant masterplans. The final Masterplanning Toolbox software described in the paper was then developed by the author as part of the scope of work for the 180 Hectare One North masterplan for Singapore’s Jurong Town Corporation, led by Zaha Hadid Architects. This plan covers the period up to 2021.

The One North project developed a masterplan based on building envelopes and the final design is shown as an aerial 3D view in figure 1.

Figure 1. One North 180 hectare masterplan for Jurong Town Corporation, Singapore.

SOFTWARE TECHNOLOGY

The software used to create the Masterplanning Toolbox was Microsoft Excel with Visual Basic object-oriented coding. File format exchange software for .DXF and .MAP was written in C++. 3D data visualisation uses the ID Software GtkRadiant-1.1-TA-beta program to compile .MAP files into .BSP files, which can be opened directly in the Quake III 3D real time walkthrough engine by id software. An option also exists for the Unreal Engine.

TOOLBOX DESCRIPTION

OVERVIEW

The overall data architecture of the Toolbox is organized using two approaches. Firstly, information related to a specific aspect of a masterplan exists on a specific data layer. This data layer is both numerical and spatial. Secondly, data on one layer that influences other data on another layer is linked between the layers and processed, or mediated, by appropriate algorithms. This effectively creates 3D through-stitching of influence between multiple layers of data. The mediation is bi-directional in a few instances.

Figure 2 shows an example of the spatial layering of data. The use of layers and linked factors is illustrated in figure 3. This shows the principle planning criteria that the Toolbox uses: building uses, transport and infrastructure, economics, and environment. Within these, there are a number of issues. Primary interactions exist between the principle planning criteria and secondary interactions exist between the subset issues.

Figure 2. Layered data in the Masterplanning Toolbox

Figure 3. Linked factors in the Masterplanning Toolbox.

FUNCTIONS

Navigation and worksheets

The tool contains 35 Excel worksheets (displayed as tabs), which are grouped into 5 sections. Spatial data sits within the worksheets. The 180 hectare site for the One North Singapore project was resolved with a 10 by 10 metre grid resolution.

Reference data

- *Massing*. Each predominant use is listed together with values for storey height and

porosity. Storey height is the height in metres of each storey for a building. The porosity value determines what percentage of the site footprint is used for building.

- *Density*. The average number of square metres occupied by a person within an area of a given predominant use, also expressing this same value as an average number of people per square metre.
- *Peopleflow*. This worksheet contains a lookup table used by the hunter-gatherer algorithm of the transport tab. For each predominant use figures are provided for each hour within a typical 24-hour daily cycle.
- *Public Transport*. Data represents attributes of tram and train transport nodes. For each of these there is a column containing the maximum capacity at a node, and also catchment information.
- *Energy*. Calculates energy usage for areas according to predominant use. These figures are useful for comparing energy use over time between different predominant uses.
- *Water Use*. Deals with expected water use for each predominant use. The main input represents average water demand for each predominant use expressed in litres per person per day.

Data processing

- *Area key*. Collates and stores essential information for the defined areas, and is used as a lookup table for the heights, plan key, energy and site selection tabs. The input data for this can be dynamically loaded from an external .xls file.
- *Plan key*. The plan key allows users to work with mapping. It shows the plan as an imported line drawing which overlays the grid of cells. The cells themselves contain values which represent the assigned areas.
- *Districts*. This worksheet allows districts to be assigned to cells within the map.
- *Availability*. Allows users to designate which cells remain available as land parcels from the areas defined in the plan worksheet.

- **Population.** This worksheet uses the figures in “plan data” and “density” to calculate the average amount of people per square metre of floor area for each cell within the map.
- **Transport.** This works in conjunction with the hunter worksheet. The map on the transport worksheet shows the average number of people potentially on the move at a given time, based on values from the density and peopleflow worksheets. The transport tab also allows users to plan for public transport by placing proposed tram stops and/or train stations around the map, then examining the effect on the people requiring transport.
- **Hunter.** This worksheet uses a ‘hunter/gatherer’ algorithm to calculate the effectiveness of a proposed transport system. The population potentially in need of transport within each cell is analyzed according to proximity of transport nodes and node capacities. Figure 4 shows the hunter/gatherer in use.

Generated outputs

- **Transport nodes.** This worksheet gives a report on the transport nodes (tram and train stations) created using the transport tab, along with properties such as location and usage information.
- **District analysis.** This worksheet produces a report on the defined districts, based on information in the districts, plan data and availability tabs. It lists all the planning areas contained within a particular district, sorted in alphabetical order.
- **Vibrancy.** This worksheet mainly uses the data in the district analysis tab to calculate a vibrancy analysis. This is based on the following formula used for the One North project: $Vibrancy = (w1 \times \text{mean population density}) + (w2 \times \text{number of different predominant use types excluding amenities}) + (w3 \times \text{number of different amenities})$. w1-w3 are editable weightings.

The hunter

Figure 4. Example of the hunter/gatherer spreadsheet in use

Plots and export

- **Plots.** This worksheet shows plots of data from key planning data in chart format. All of these charts update automatically if their source data is edited. Examples are shown in figure 5.
- **Export.** There are two main sections in this worksheet, allowing data to be export to 3D .DXF or to the 3D real time walkthrough program.

What if? Testing

The tool is able to generate “what if” scenarios very quickly for evaluation by a design team. These scenarios can be created for example by varying numerical indices such as the energy use of buildings, or by modify building height envelopes. Any change of this nature then ripples through the tool and adjusts all the inter-related criteria, updating the reporting and graphs that are available as output. Hence, a designer can adjust a neighbourhood and understand the implications of the changes, even in terms of the qualitative aspects of vibrancy. The Singapore mixed use plan is shown in Figure 6.

DISCUSSION

Two innovative algorithms, one for the ‘hunter-gatherer’ transport node algorithm, and another for measurement of the ‘vibrancy’ of an area in quantitative terms were able to produce results of value for the design team.

The tool is intended to cater for a variety of users, including architects, urban designers, planners, city authorities, and technical consultants. The tool's outputs were understandable by this diverse user group, as were the 3D real time walkthroughs.

The development time frame for the Singapore masterplan meant that although the Masterplanning Toolbox was developed as part of the scope of this project, the design team was only able to make a limited evaluation of its capabilities for the project. However, the team was able to input significantly into the scoping and review of the tool's features.

Figure 5. Examples of data output plots: (1) building heights, and (2) energy use over 24 hours by building type.

Despite a bespoke data entry interface the Excel-based 2D system proved to be quite awkward for novice users, and this represented a notable barrier to entry for the system, particularly when setting up

Figure 6. The mixed use plan for Singapore.

the initial data set. The grid-based approach used a granularity of 10 by 10 metres which, although suitable for the One North masterplan is not sufficiently high for smaller scale masterplan. Although the grid resolution could be increased to 1 by 1 metres, a reprogramming exercise that accommodates adjacent customisable polygons would be worth considering.

An example of a 3D generated output is shown in figure 7. The graphics from the Quake III engine are fairly crude. A version of the Masterplanning Tool with a better graphical user interface, possibly using the CryEngine 3 game engine is now under

Figure 7. Realtime 3D model, output generated by the Quake III engine.

consideration. The advantages that this would provide for designers of real-time visualization and analysis are clear.

CONCLUSIONS

The advantages of the Masterplanning Toolbox may be summarised:-

- Demonstrates the impact of selected urban factors on one another in real time
- Allows ‘What if?’ Scenario testing
- Gives scenario and phasing comparisons when modifying designs
- Can be used as a long term ‘dynamic’ planning tool by city authorities
- Provides 3D walkthroughs for planners, consultation and public exhibition

Although there are many areas in which the program needs to be improved going forward, including the range of dependencies that it considers - shown in figure 8 - the Masterplanning Tool used in its current form has the potential to facilitate better masterplanning at the concept stage with more quantifiable results.

The Masterplanning Tool itself is relatively simple with low computational requirements when compared with the sophisticated tools in the other

Although the Masterplanning Tool has the functionality to potentially continue to be used by a city authority over the subsequent years that a masterplan takes to implement, this has not yet been tested. The author believes that the absence of a friendly and easy to use graphical user interface is a current obstacle to this type of prolonged use. Such extended usage would allow refinements and practical variations to be tested in an informed manner against the original intent. In this application, design ‘DNA’ could form an envelop of parameters to ensure that variations over time maintain this intent.

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Figure 8. The current dependencies of the Masterplanning Tool, software system diagram.

six categories for city design. However, the Masterplanning Tool is intended to complement these other tools rather than replace them.

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